

Entropic nature of the world.

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Annotation.

Entropy interaction is introduced as the fifth fundamental interaction. It is a common base characteristic of fundamental interactions, which allows us to give a unified description of classical, quantum and relativistic effects. Gravity quantization was carried out using entropy interaction and shows how the introduction of the entropic interaction allows us to combine the Schrödinger and Fokker-Planck equations into one structure and to describe both quantum and relativistic mechanics within the framework of one approach and let us to explain and calculate observed phenomena, starting with the refraction of light, the process of measurement and continuing with relativistic and quantum effects, the quantization of gravity and the origin and expansion of the universe.

Among the relativistic effects are the constancy and limiting value of the speed of light, the growth of the mass of objects at increasing speed, the observed expansion of the universe, the dependence of the rhythm of time in physical systems on changes in entropy, on their relative speed and the magnitude of the gravitational field in which they are located, the deflection of light from a rectilinear trajectory near massive bodies, which is associated with the regular shift of the perihelion of Mercury when approaching the sun, as well as the phenomenon of periastron of double stars.

In quantum mechanics, entropy interaction allows one to explain measurement problems by “entanglement” of the observer and objects of measurement, explains and allows us to calculate such phenomena of classical and quantum physics as interference and diffraction by using small-angle scattering of photons and elementary particles in a weak potential field, abandoning wave-particle duality.

The Principle of 100% efficiency of mathematics is used as a guiding role in modeling natural processes. The random nature of natural phenomena is explained. The refusal to use the concept of field is justified. The essence of virtual matter is clarified. The variant of the origin and extension of the universe is considered as a consequence of a change in its entropy as a result of the bifurcation of the distribution of the density of virtual objects in a local region of world space.

Keywords

Fundamental interactions, entropy interaction, virtual matter, mass defect, bifurcation, big bang, gravity quantization, expansion of the universe.

I. Introduction

Niels Bohr once said [1]: “*A new theory, to be correct, must be quite crazy.*” And we would like to agree with this statement, in principle. The key to understanding the laws of nature, their mathematical description and subsequent interpretation of the obtained experimental and theoretical data is the scientific explanation of the observed phenomena. Any theory that appears consistent and reflects the truth must explain the essence of laws of nature and reconcile experimental facts with their theoretical description. This should lead to understanding of the phenomena being studied and, as a consequence, provide the results arising from these requirements predictive of the power of theory.

Classical physics in our familiar environment, quantum mechanical approach to microworld phenomena, relativistic approach to phenomena of the macro world and cosmology successfully describe the observed patterns, but at the same time rely *on a number of postulates*

that have no acceptable explanations. Therefore, although to date not a single fact has been discovered that does not agree with the predictions of the mentioned theories, this does not mean that they are perfect and reflect true reality.

II. Simulation of natural phenomena

When modeling natural phenomena, one should rely on *The principle of 100% effectiveness of mathematics* [2], which reads: "For any reality (natural or artificial) there are conditions for its observation and a precisely defined mathematical structure that describes this reality with any predetermined finite accuracy. Conversely, for any precisely defined mathematical structure there exists (is not prohibited from existing) reality (natural or artificial) together with the conditions for its observation, which is described by this structure."

The principle of 100% effectiveness of mathematics contains *The principle of knowability of any reality* with the help of appropriate mathematical structures [2].

These principles presuppose the possibility of various mathematical modeling of the same natural phenomenon and obtaining observed patterns with sufficient accuracy. Note also that the widespread belief that any deviation from the predictions of the theory will mean the failure of the theory is incorrect.

In our opinion, this will only mean that the model used by the theory does not include this phenomenon. Mathematical models of existing reality should be considered as abstract entities, in contrast to the material entities that are the simulated phenomena.

III. Fundamental Interactions

For the evolution of any isolated system, certain processes (physical, chemical, biological, etc.) must occur in it. All processes are based on interactions between the objects that make up the system. These are the (so-called) fundamental interactions: gravitational, electromagnetic, and nuclear (weak and strong). In our previous publications [3-5], we added to them the fifth fundamental interaction - entropic interaction.

It is understood as the mutual influence of open systems on each other through the transfer of information about their states, coordinated changes in entropy and the mutual tendency to transition to more probable states. During the entropic interaction of material objects, there is no exchange of energy between them, carried by the corresponding energy quanta. These objects are combined into one system with a common entropy value and processes are launched in them, seeking to equalize its value in all parts of this system, thereby increasing the entropy of the entire system and transferring the system into a more balanced state.

Entropy interaction is not a consequence of the existence of any entropic charge and accompanying field. It cannot be said that it spreads in space. "from point to point" and transfers energy or any material objects. It reflects a certain "order" in space, its structure, symmetry, "state" of space and the physical systems located in it, initiates certain processes in them, changes the free energy, behavior and evolution of these systems and the entire space as a whole.

Fundamental interactions change the state of the system. They change the probability W of a given state, which in quantum mechanics is given by the square of the modulus of the wave function $|\Psi|^2$. In thermodynamics, the probability W determined by the free energy of the system G , and in Newtonian physics and in the theory of relativity (special and general) does not appear at all, since there each state is considered as deterministic, i.e. clearly defined.

The fifth of the four fundamental interactions listed above causes a change in the entropy of the system, and its change initiates (in turn) one or more other fundamental interactions, launching a corresponding process designed to balance the amount of entropy in different parts of the system. Those five fundamental interactions are mutually consistent and initiate each other, as shown in our work [6]. The introduction to physics of the entropic interaction is a

common fundamental idea for all observable natural phenomena.

The change in entropy at any part of the system, i.e. inside any of its subsystems, changes simultaneously [7] by the same amount of entropy of the entire system. We can say that information about this change is transmitted instantly to all parts of the system, regardless of their distance from each other. In other words, *there is a long range action*

A change in entropy initiates a corresponding process involving other fundamental interactions, which propagates throughout the system at a finite speed, i.e. according to the principle of short-range action.

The transfer of entropic information from one part of the system to another (or between different open systems) should be considered as entropic interaction between these areas (or systems). The observed behavior of such thermodynamic systems as ideal gas or dilute solutions of low molecular weight substances and flexible macromolecules is an excellent illustration of *entropic interaction* at the molecular level. It manifests itself as their mutual repulsion or attraction, carried out due to Van der Waals forces, "*included*" entropic interaction of molecules. Random processes occurring in these systems implement entropic interaction at the molecular level and direct the systems to more probable (and more equilibrium) states.

The concept of entropic interaction was previously used in the subjunctive mood. For example, macromolecular units as *if entropically repel from each other at close distances and entropically attract over long distances* [8,9]. In modern scientific approaches, entropic interaction is considered as really existing [10-12].

IV. Combining quantum mechanics and relativity within one theory.

One of the fundamental problems of modern theoretical physics, its "Holy Grail," is the unification of quantum mechanics and the theory of relativity within one theory. In this article we will try to solve this problem and thereby quantize the phenomenon of gravity. It should immediately be noted that we refuse to consider the concept of "field" as a physical reality, assigning it a place in abstract reality.

V.A.Fock once wrote [13] that *it is important, when interpreting quantum mechanics, to distinguish between the potentially possible and the possible realized.* (In this regard, one might add that the *potentially possible is an abstract entity, while the realized is a material or real entity, an objective reality.*

The wave function of quantum mechanics, in particular, is not any material entity, but is only a convenient mathematical abstraction. Its sudden change does not represent a physical process, which, unlike the wave function, is a material entity and changes with the production of experience.

In the same article [13] Fock wrote: "*Obviously, this kind of instantaneous change in the wave function does not agree with the concept of field.*" The field is only a mathematical possibility for describing observable physical phenomena and does not represent a material entity whose quantum disturbances are elementary particles (as they are now trying to interpret abstract mathematical results obtained in quantum field theory).

(Note, that, using the concept of "fields", we, actually, return to the irrevocably rejected concept of the ether.)

In particular, this article attempts to explain the probabilistic nature of physical laws not by the fact of the existence of parallel universes (the possible existence of which is not denied), as is done in Everett's approach [14], but based on the tendency of nonequilibrium physical systems to pass into more equilibrium (more probable) states with a lower value of free energy, using as one of the possibilities *real random emission of "energy quanta"* by all objects, both in the microcosm and in the macrocosm.

V. A note on the interference of light: a critique of wave-particle duality.

It should be noted that over the last century, the interpretation of wave-particle duality [15] using the principle of complementarity has been accepted as true. However, it should be remembered that the wave in these experiments is not a material entity, like the particles it simulates. It is a product of a mathematical description of the movement of the corresponding particles, their distribution in space as a result of interaction with macroscopic objects, which in these experiments are slits and experimenters. Einstein, in his article “On a Heuristic Point of View Concerning the Origin and Transformation of Light” [16], emphasized the contrast between the ideas of physics about the structure of matter and the wave structure of light. According to the assumption he made in this article, “the energy of a beam of light emerging from each point is not distributed continuously over an ever-increasing volume, but is composed of a finite number of indivisible energy quanta localized in space, absorbed or arising only as a whole”. In interference experiments with light or an ensemble of particles, the wave cannot be directly seen or felt (like, for example, a wave on water). It is not reality, but is only a certain mathematical abstraction, convenient for predicting the results of experiments, but not for explaining them. Yes, the wave packet collapses into a specific wave function during the interference process, but the material entities described in this case - elementary particles - remain unchanged and are distributed in space in a strictly defined way. Explaining this distribution by the wave properties of elementary particles or their interaction with “shadow” particles [17] from numerous parallel universes, as well as declaring on this basis, the existence of these universes seems unfounded (although the existence of parallel universes or the “multiverse” is very possible and will be discussed below).

Now, we will repeat the explanation of interference from our paper [18]. For this case, in the monograph (Landau and Lifshitz Quantum mechanics) , within the framework of classical mechanics, the following expression was obtained that relates the angle $\Theta(\varrho)$ of particle scattering in a weak potential field $U(r)$ with the magnitude of this field:

$$\Theta(\varrho) = -\frac{2\varrho}{mv_{\infty}^2} \int_{\varrho}^{\infty} \frac{dU(r)}{dr} \frac{dr}{\sqrt{r^2 - \varrho^2}} \quad (1)$$

Here ϱ is the impact distance (i.e., the distance to the nearest point of the orbit to the origin), m is the mass of the particle, v_{∞} is its velocity at infinity.

Relation (1) allows, by setting $U(r)$, to find $\Theta(\varrho)$ and obtain an interference pattern. To do this, we reverse the problem and require, by setting $\Theta(\varrho)$, to find $U(\varrho)$. Then equation (1) turns into an integral equation of the 1st kind. To express $U(\varrho)$ in terms $\Theta(\varrho)$ it is necessary to obtain a solution to this equation.

Denoting

$$-\frac{2}{mv_{\infty}^2} = \frac{1}{r_0}, \quad \frac{dU(r)}{dr} = 2r_0 V(r) \quad (2)$$

and setting

$$\Theta(\varrho) = \varrho \Theta_1(\varrho^2), \quad V(r) = r V_1(r^2), \quad (3)$$

$$r^2 = y, \quad \varrho^2 = z, \quad (4)$$

we reduce (1) to the form

$$\Theta_1(z) = \int_z^{\infty} (y - z)^{-\frac{1}{2}} V_1(y) dy \quad (5)$$

Transposing (5), we get equation (6) that is nothing more than a version of the Abel integral equation, i.e. a special case of the Volterra integral equation of the 1st kind with a difference kernel:

$$\Theta_1(z) = \int_0^z (z - y)^{-\frac{1}{2}} V_1(y) dy \quad (6)$$

With respect to this equation, it is known that it refers to well posed problems (among the problems of this class) and its solution can be obtained by the Laplace transform. This solution has the form

$$V_1(z) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^z (z - x)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \frac{d}{dx} \Theta_1(x) dx \quad (7)$$

Transposing (7), referring to (2), (3), and putting this time

$$z = r^2, \quad x = \varrho^2, \quad (8)$$

we come to the solution of the original equation (1)

$$-\frac{1}{mv_{\infty}^2} \frac{dU(r)}{dr} = \frac{r}{\pi} \int_{r^2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{r^2 \sqrt{\varrho^2 - r^2}} \frac{d}{d\varrho} \left(\frac{\Theta(\varrho)}{\varrho} \right) d\varrho \quad (9)$$

Now it is necessary to obtain from (9) the potential $V(r)$, leading to the a priori specified dependence of $\Theta(\varrho)$. To do this, note that

$$-r \int_{r_m^2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\varrho^2 - r^2}} \frac{d}{d\varrho} \left(\frac{\Theta(\varrho)}{\varrho} \right) d\varrho = \frac{d}{dr} \int_{r_m^2}^{\infty} \sqrt{\varrho^2 - r^2} \frac{d}{d\varrho} \left(\frac{\Theta(\varrho)}{\varrho} \right) d\varrho, \quad (10)$$

Using (10), we find that (9) in the approximation turns into

$$\frac{1}{mv_{\infty}^2} \frac{dU(r)}{dr} = \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{d}{dr} \int_{r_m^2}^{\infty} \sqrt{\varrho^2 - r^2} \frac{d}{d\varrho} \left(\frac{\Theta(\varrho)}{\varrho} \right) d\varrho \quad (11)$$

Whence

$$\frac{1}{mv_{\infty}^2} U(r) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{r_m^2}^{\infty} \sqrt{\varrho^2 - r^2} \frac{d}{d\varrho} \left(\frac{\Theta(\varrho)}{\varrho} \right) d\varrho + C, \quad (12)$$

where C is the integration constant.

Assuming in (12) $r_m \approx r \rightarrow \infty$, we see that $C=0$. Thus, the desired dependence takes the form

$$U(r) = \frac{mv_\infty^2}{\pi} \int_{r_m^2}^{\infty} \sqrt{q^2 - r^2} \frac{d}{dq} \left(\frac{\Theta(q)}{q} \right) dq \quad (13)$$

Note that if the function $\Theta(q)$ is even, then the entire integrand in (13) also turns out to be even, and relation (13) then allows writing

$$U(r) = U^-(r) + U^+(r) = \frac{mv_\infty^2}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{-r_m^2} \sqrt{q^2 - r^2} \frac{d}{dq} \left(\frac{\Theta(q)}{q} \right) dq + \frac{mv_\infty^2}{2\pi} \int_{r_m^2}^{\infty} \sqrt{q^2 - r^2} \frac{d}{dq} \left(\frac{\Theta(q)}{q} \right) dq, \quad (14)$$

i.e. $U(r)$ represents the force effect of two identical potentials oriented symmetrically about the y-axis and localized in the regions $(-\infty, -r_m^2]$ and $[r_m^2, \infty)$ respectively.

Obviously, for further analysis it is sufficient to deal with the relation

$$U^+(r) = \frac{mv_\infty^2}{2\pi} \int_{r_m^2}^{\infty} \sqrt{q^2 - r^2} \frac{d}{dq} \left(\frac{\Theta(q)}{q} \right) dq \quad (15)$$

Thus, for each a priori specified class of interference patterns $\Theta(q)$ (due to (15)) corresponds to the class of potentials $U^+(r)$, generating $\Theta(q)$. Thus, the class of pictures

$$\Theta(q) = \alpha e^{-aq^2} (\beta + \gamma \cos \lambda q) \quad (16)$$

generated by the class of potentials

$$U^+(r) = \frac{mv_\infty^2}{2\pi} \int_{r_m^2}^{\infty} \sqrt{q^2 - r^2} d \left[\frac{\alpha e^{-aq^2} (\beta + \gamma \cos \lambda q)}{q} \right], \quad (17)$$

which, after integration by parts and taking into account $r_m \approx r$, take the form

$$U^+(r) = - \frac{mv_\infty^2}{2\pi} \int_{r_m^2}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha e^{-aq^2} (\beta + \gamma \cos \lambda q)}{\sqrt{q^2 - r^2}} dq, \quad (18)$$

Note that since each particle, generally speaking, has its own impact distance q , then the interference pattern will be the same as a result, regardless of whether the particles arrive at the scattering center sequentially one at a time or are directed to it as an ensemble.

Consider an example.

$$\text{Let } \alpha = \frac{1}{2}, a = \beta = \gamma = 1, \lambda = 2.$$

Then

$$\Theta(\varrho) = e^{-\varrho^2} \cos^2 \varrho \quad (19)$$

This dependence well approximates the observed interference patterns when particles pass through two slits.

Accordingly

$$U^+(r) = - \frac{mv_\infty^2}{2\pi} \int_{r_m^2}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\varrho^2} \cos^2 \varrho}{\sqrt{\varrho^2 - r^2}} d\varrho, \quad (20)$$

But $r < \varrho$, hence

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{\varrho^2 - r^2}} = \frac{1}{\varrho} \left(1 - \frac{r^2}{\varrho^2}\right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{1}{\varrho} - \frac{1}{2\varrho^3} r^2 + \frac{3}{8\varrho^5} r^4 - \frac{5}{16\varrho^7} r^6 + \dots \quad (21)$$

Then (20) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} U^+(r) = & - \frac{mv_\infty^2}{2\pi} \left\{ \int_{r_m^2}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\varrho^2} \cos^2 \varrho}{\varrho} d\varrho - \frac{1}{2} r^2 \int_{r_m^2}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\varrho^2} \cos^2 \varrho}{\varrho^3} d\varrho + \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{3}{8} r^4 \int_{r_m^2}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\varrho^2} \cos^2 \varrho}{\varrho^5} d\varrho - \frac{5}{16} r^6 \int_{r_m^2}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\varrho^2} \cos^2 \varrho}{\varrho^7} d\varrho + \dots \right\}, \quad (22) \end{aligned}$$

moreover, all integrals in (22) converge and are positive values.

Therefore, $U^+(r)$ is a structure of the form

$$U^+(r) = - a_0 + a_2 r^2 - a_4 r^4 + a_6 r^6 - \dots, \quad (23)$$

where $U^+(r)$ in the approximation of retention in expansion (23) of the first four terms.

The change in the areas of increase and decrease of the function $U^+(r)$ physically means the corresponding switching of the sign of the force action.

Figure 1.

A given interference pattern showing the dependence of the deflection angle of particles $\theta(\rho)$ on the impact distance ρ when they are scattered by two slits in a weak potential field $U(r)$.

Figure 2.

View of the potential $U(r)$ that creates the interference pattern shown in Fig. 2.

Thus, the interference pattern from a stream of particles can be obtained without any recourse to the wave mechanism and wave-particle duality.

VI. Explanation of the random nature of natural phenomena.

We know that the molecules that make up all substances have a certain kinetic energy, i.e. moving. Their thermal movement occurs chaotically. What is the reason for this movement? Us *reliably* is known that any object whose temperature on an absolute scale is not zero emits energy

in accordance with the Stefan-Boltzmann law $E = kT^4$ and, if the temperature of this object is higher than the ambient temperature, it transfers heat to this environment in accordance with Fourier's law [19].

$$q = -k_1 \text{grad } T, \quad (24)$$

where q is the heat flux density, $k = 1.38 \times 10^{-23}$ J/K - Boltzmann's constant, k_1 - coefficient of thermal conductivity, $\text{grad } T$ - temperature gradient, and the object and the environment in formula (24) are considered as a general system in which heat is transferred from the hotter part, i.e. from the object, to the less heated part, i.e. environment.

This means that such objects and the environment in which they are located are in a nonequilibrium state and tend to move to a more probable (more equilibrium) state. To do this, they must, interacting entropically, reduce their free energy, which they achieve by releasing energy in the form of quanta in the infrared range.

These energy quanta, i.e. photons are emitted *randomly* in all directions and, naturally, discretely with a certain frequency. With the emission of each quantum, these molecules receive reactive impulses (recoil impulses) in the direction opposite to radiation (similar to the Mössbauer effect [20]). In addition, each molecule receives certain impulses by absorbing some (so-called resonant) photons emitted by neighboring molecules.

It is important to say that molecules and the objects consisting of them emit not only photons, but also other "energy quanta", for example, gravitational or quanta associated with strong or weak nuclear interaction. (Elementary particles may also have this property.) Under the influence of all received impulses, the molecules move chaotically. The random nature of this movement (which can be described in detail as stochastic process, consisting of a sequence random steps in some mathematical space [21]) leads these molecules to move away from each other, since in this case they have more free places for their location (the so-called "excluded volume" decreases) i.e. in the case of gaseous substances to the observed expansion of their cloud. It should also be noted that the cloud of molecules from this example can be replaced with just one molecule. Then, in accordance with the Ergodic theorem [22], which proves that the ensemble average is equal to the time average, it is possible to monitor not the totality of molecules in the cloud, but just one molecule. The probability of its location at any arbitrarily chosen point in a limited space will not differ from the correspondingly renormalized density ρ molecules in an expanding cloud. This means that the random walk of this molecule will occur in such a way that this probability tends to become the same in any local region of a given space.

That is, in accordance with Boltzmann's H-theorem [23], the entropy of a system consisting of a local region of space and a molecule wandering in it (with the internal energy remaining constant) tends to increase (as does the probability of the molecule moving away from its initial and subsequent locations).

VII. The concept of virtual matter.

Recently, the concepts of virtual reality and virtual particles have been repeatedly used [24]. We will try to put into these concepts a relatively new, but fairly general content.

*Let us define as virtual the state of an object that is not observed, i.e. really, **as if**, does not exist, but has energy and entropy and can arise (manifest, be observed) under certain conditions that lead to a change in entropy.* If an object has any measurable observable property, we call it *material object* and say that it is *material essence*. Both material and virtual objects are in *world space*. By space, we should understand *limitless empty container (or simply emptiness)*, in which these objects are located, occupy a certain position, can move in any direction and exhibit certain properties. About a part of space filled only with virtual objects, we say that it is filled with a *physical vacuum*, possessing a certain energy.

Energy is understood reflects the ability of virtual and material objects to do work.

As a clear example in which material and virtual objects appear, let us turn to the concept of mass. It is associated with one of the components of the internal energy of the system, $E = mc^2$, and its free energy G , which the system seeks to reduce in order to move to a more probable state. Being at the same time *gravitational charge of the object*, a measure of gravity, inertia and energy, (and also, to some extent, a measure of matter in an object) *mass manifests itself* only when an object is exposed to any force (i.e. during the interaction of various objects). If there is no such influence (or it is negligible, for example, when the distance between objects is sufficiently large) or the resultant of all forces acting on the object is equal to zero, then the mass of the object does not manifest itself in any way. In these cases she seems to really not exist. (The same can be said about other characteristics of material objects, for example, about their “appearance”, electric charge, and so on.) Electric charge and (theoretically) the field generated by it “*manifest*”, if the charge is acted upon by another electric charge. An object becomes visible when it reflects or emits light falling on it. Niels Bohr formulated this pattern as follows: “*There is no reality that does not depend on the way it is observed.*”

In classical physics, two types of mass are distinguished: gravitational and inertial. Speaking about the general theory of relativity, these masses are often considered identical, producing a gravitational field, and refer to the principle of equivalence [25]. At this time, it is generally accepted that the *source of the field* (i.e. the concept that we abandon) is the *charge* (for example, gravitational mass, electric charge, etc.) of this field. It is stated that if there are no charges in space, then there are no corresponding fields there. But what about the fact that when an object accelerates, there is no mass to which the accelerated object is attracted? This means that the corresponding field does not appear in the sense in which the field created by the gravitational mass is interpreted. Indeed, if next to accelerate the object will not be an accelerated object, it will not experience any interaction with the inertial mass of the accelerated object (meaning gravitational attraction) which *as if* experiences an accelerated object. Therefore, we cannot assume that the inertial and gravitational masses are identical, and for the inertial mass we cannot use model geometric interpretation of space curvature, *reliably working locally* for gravitational mass. Inertial mass of an object (as well as gravitational mass) *manifests itself locally*, when a force acts on an object and a selected direction appears in space, directed along the action of this force, and the entropy of the object decreases accordingly. But unlike gravitational mass, inert mass does not create a field. She acts like an object, outraged by an object that creates a force and thereby creates a corresponding acceleration. The emergence of this force can be explained by a decrease in the entropy of the object, leading to a violation of the isotropic nature of the emission of energy quanta. *This radiation becomes more directed in the direction opposite to the action of the force*, towards the direction of acceleration.

Another example that involves material and virtual objects. From nuclear physics we know that the mass of an atomic nucleus is always less than the total mass of its constituent nucleons (as, for example, the mass of nucleons is less than the mass of their constituent quarks). In nuclear physics this *mass defect* [26] explains her “*consumption*” on the binding energy of nucleons in the nucleus of an atom. Moreover, the mass defect is reversible: the mass spent on binding energy does not disappear without a trace, and if the nucleus could be “disassembled” into the nucleons included in it, then each of them would have its own initial mass.

According to the General Theory of Relativity, the presence of bodies with mass in space changes the geometry of space, bends it, and makes it non-Euclidean (“concave”). “Curved” space has Riemannian geometry. *This approach should be considered as a model mathematical abstraction*. Using this terminology, we can say that the “consumption” of mass on the binding energy caused by the mutual attraction of bodies reduces the gravitational curvature of space (its “concavity”). And the reversibility of the mass defect says that these interacting bodies still

continue to be present in space, but some part of them is in a virtual state.

*In many cosmological theories, the World space is considered as “empty”, but possessing metrics and energy. We believe that empty **physical** space cannot have a metric. **The metric of any space is defined (exists) on a set of elements**, defining the “distance” between them. In an abstract mathematical space, its elements can be its points, determined by the corresponding coordinates. And the elements of “real physical space” must be some “objects”, i.e. material or virtual entities that can be directly or indirectly observed. To speak about the geometry of “emptiness”, about the curvature of “empty physical space”, in our opinion, looks inappropriate. To confirm this, it should be said that the “gravitational curvature” of physical space, which is good in models **local areas** near massive bodies, is not confirmed by large-scale measurements made at intergalactic distances. However, the objection expressed here to metric **world space** is removed if we assume that it is not empty, but filled with matter in real or virtual states, as they were defined by us earlier. In this case, there are no objections to the metric of general relativity, as an abstract mathematical entity that successfully models the gravitational interaction of material objects.*

VIII. Deflection towards the sun of the light beam and displacement of the perihelion of Mercury.

The regular displacement of the perihelion of Mercury as it approaches the sun and the periastron of double stars (pulsars) can be explained and calculated, as demonstrated in our work [18], within the framework of geometric optics using the eikonal model [27] (where a ray of light is considered as the movement of a material point) not by the curvature of space, but by the using the entropic interaction to lower the free energy of the system by reducing the emission of “energy quanta” towards the sun or towards each of the double stars.

We will repeat here consideration of the issue from publication [18]

The deviation of a light beam from a rectilinear trajectory observed during a solar eclipse can be explained not by the curvature of space, but by the entropic interaction of photons of the light beam with the components of the solar atmosphere.

The space surrounding the sun is filled with its radiation. It is not uniform. A beam of light, falling into this region of space, further increases its heterogeneity and, trying to eliminate it, tends to *mix* with the components of the solar atmosphere, deviating towards the sun. This increases the entropy of the sun-light beam system, reduces its free energy, and puts the system in a more probable state. This deflection of the light beam is an objective reality, which is well modeled in the General Theory of Relativity by a mathematical abstraction in a geometric form, which predicts the “curvature” of space and the subordination of Riemann's geometry, and not Euclid's.

The result of the entropic interaction leading to the deflection of the beam can also be quite simply described by another model (without involving the idea of space curvature) within the framework of geometric optics using the eikonal model, i.e., optical path U of a beam of light (which is, like the curvature of space, a mathematical abstraction). In particular, the optical-mechanical analogy (where a beam of light is considered as the movement of a material point), used in the eikonal, played an important role in the development of quantum mechanics.

We will rely on the eikonal equation

$$(\text{grad } U)^2 = n^2, \quad (25)$$

where the function $U(r)$ is called eikonal, which in Greek (εἰκών) means an image, and the light refractive index n is some function of the x :

$$n=n(x). \quad (26)$$

Equation (25) describes the ray trajectory in geometrical optics.

Eikonal in geometric optics is analogous to action in mechanics, which allows us to imagine an analytical transition from Maupertuis's principle of least action to Fermat's principle, according to which light propagates along a path that takes extreme time to travel.

In terms of the eikonal, Fermat's principle means the realization of the equality

$$\delta U = 0 \quad (27)$$

The reliance on the idea of the eikonal has two goals. Namely, without any recourse to the concept of gravitation: 1) to obtain correct qualitative pictures of the deflection of a beam passing by the Sun and the displacement of Mercury's perihelion, and 2) by varying the parameters of the eikonal, to arrive at reasonable (average) values of the refractive indices in the solar atmosphere and to the observed quantitative values both the deflection angle of the beam and the precession of the planet.

For simplicity, we will assume that the transmitted ray belongs entirely to the section of the sun's atmosphere by the XOY in the Cartesian coordinate system, whose axis OY is normal to the sun's surface. Then equation (25) will take the form

$$\left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial y}\right)^2 = n^2(x) \quad (28)$$

The solution of equation (28) should have the structure

$$U = f(x) + \alpha y \quad (29)$$

where α is the constant of integration.

Substituting (29) into (28), we obtain

$$f(x) = \pm \int \sqrt{n^2(x) - \alpha^2} dx, \quad (30)$$

whence the eikonal U defined by equation (29) takes the form

$$U = \alpha y \pm \int \sqrt{n^2(x) - \alpha^2} dx, \quad (31)$$

In accordance with Fermat's principle, (stating that a beam of light elects a path in space that requires extreme time for its passage), the eikonal U must maintain a stationary value, including by α , i.e., it is necessary that

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial \alpha} = 0 \quad (32)$$

Whence

$$y = \pm \int \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{n^2(x) - \alpha^2}} dx, \quad (33)$$

This is the beam equation.

We write $n(x)$ using $n_0(x)$, choosing the last function so that the difference between the integrands in (33) built on $n(x)$ and $n_0(x)$ differs approximately by a small value μ . The smaller μ , the more accurate this approximation. When μ equal to zero, these functions coincide. That is, we will use equation (34) instead of (33).

$$y = \pm \int \left(\frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{n_0^2(x) - \alpha^2}} + \mu \right) dx, \quad (34)$$

which describes the beam the better, the less μ .

We approximate $n_0(x)$ as

$$n_0^2(x) = 1 + \frac{q^2}{1+x^2}, \quad (35)$$

where q is a parameter, $0 < q \leq q_0$.

Let further be γ^2 -coefficient corresponding to the best quadratic approximation on some interval of the function $(1 + x^2)$ by function x^2 . Then, substituting (35) into (34) and integrating, we find

$$y - \beta = \mu x \pm \frac{\alpha\gamma}{1-\alpha^2} \sqrt{q^2 + (1 - \alpha^2)(1 + x^2)}, \quad (36)$$

where β is the constant of integration. From the requirement of symmetry of the beam with respect to the axis OX , accept $\beta = 0$.

Will analyze two possibilities:

1). Let for the light beam be satisfied

$$\mu = 0, \quad 1 - \alpha^2 > 0$$

Then (36) turns into (37):

$$\frac{y^2}{b_1^2} - \frac{x^2}{a_1^2} = 1, \quad (37)$$

where

$$b_1^2 = \frac{\alpha^2 \gamma^2}{1-\alpha^2} \left(1 + \frac{q^2}{1-\alpha^2}\right) \quad (38)$$

$$a_1^2 = 1 + \frac{q^2}{1-\alpha^2} \quad (39)$$

Thus, a ray of light, passing through the atmosphere of the sun, goes around the sun along a hyperbola (38). The angle Θ of deviation of the beam from the straight line is the angle between the asymptotes of this hyperbola

$$y = \frac{b_1}{a_1} x, \quad y = -\frac{b_1}{a_1} x, \quad (40)$$

I.e., Θ is determined by formula

$$tg\Theta = \frac{2a_1 b_1}{a_1^2 - b_1^2} \quad (41)$$

Our problem further, by varying the value of the refractive index $n_0(x)$, i.e., the value q , is to obtain a numerically observed estimate of the deflection angle Θ .

First of all, we note that the exponent $n_0(x)$ is close to unity, i.e., q is very small. It is also known from observations that the angle Θ is also very small. Therefore,

$$tg\Theta \approx \Theta \quad (42)$$

From (38) and (39) we have.

$$b_1^2 = \frac{\alpha^2 \gamma^2}{1-\alpha^2} a_1^2 \quad (43)$$

Substituting (42) and (43) into (41), we see that

$$\alpha^2 \ll 1, \quad 1 - \alpha^2 \approx 1 \quad (44)$$

and as a result we arrive at the equality

$$\Theta \approx 2\alpha\gamma \quad (45)$$

The given relationships allow to replace (38) and (39) by approximations

$$a_1^2 \approx 1, \quad b_1^2 \approx \frac{1}{4}\Theta^2(1 + q^2), \quad (46)$$

which, in particular, show that

$$b_1^2 \ll a_1^2 \quad (47)$$

These relations allow us to replace the eccentricity ϵ of the hyperbola with approximations

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{b_1^2} \sqrt{a_1^2 + b_1^2} \approx \frac{a_1}{b_1} \approx \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2}\Theta\sqrt{1+q^2}} \approx \frac{2}{\Theta} \quad (48)$$

Since $\Theta \ll 1$, then $\epsilon \gg 1$. This means that the branches of the hyperbola are strongly "pressed" to the axis OX .

Further, from (45) and (48) we have

$$\epsilon^2 = \frac{a_1^2 + b_1^2}{b_1^2} \approx \frac{1 + \frac{1}{4}\Theta^2(1+q^2)}{\frac{1}{4}\Theta^2(1+q^2)} \approx \frac{1}{\frac{1}{4}\Theta^2} \quad (49)$$

$$\frac{1}{4}\Theta^2 q^2 \approx q^2 \quad (50)$$

Therefore, the angle sought is related to the value q by equation

$$\Theta^2 \approx \frac{4q^2}{1+q^2} \quad (51)$$

Now, by varying the value of q in (94), we can find (restore) the refractive index of the atmosphere, leading to the observed value of the deflection angle Θ .

This procedure, as you can easily see, leads to the following values:

$$q \approx 4.19 \times 10^{-6} \quad (52)$$

$$\Theta \approx 8.39 \times 10^{-6} \text{ radians} \approx 1.73'' \quad (53)$$

The last number is in full agreement with the observed value of the deflection angle of the beam passing by the sun.

Finally, we note that there is the function $n_0^2(x)$ in (35). Our goal is to restore $n_0(x)$. But in the approximations under consideration, with an accuracy of the order of 10^{-6} , we can write $n_0^2(x) \approx 1 + q^2 \approx 1 + 2q + q^2 \approx (1 + q)^2$ (54)

Then the refractive index of the medium itself, leading to the deflection angle (96), obtains on the basis of (94) the estimate

$$n_0(x) \approx 1 + q \approx 1 + 4.19 \times 10^{-6} = 1.00000419 \quad (55)$$

Note that an independent control carried out according to the standard formula for the refractive index following from Snell's law gives an identical value.

Let us turn to the second possible values of the parameters μ and α :

$$\mu \neq 0, \quad 0 < \alpha^2 - 1 < q^2$$

Then (79) goes into (99),

$$\frac{x^2}{a_2^2} - 2\mu_0 xy + \frac{y^2}{b_2^2} = 1, \quad (56)$$

where

$$a_2^2 = \frac{\alpha^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2 - 1} \left(\frac{q^2}{\alpha^2 - 1} - 1 \right) / \left(\mu^2 + \frac{\alpha^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2 - 1} \right) \quad (57)$$

$$\mu_0 = \frac{\mu}{\frac{\alpha^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2 - 1} \left(\frac{q^2}{\alpha^2 - 1} - 1 \right)} = \frac{\mu}{b_2^2} \quad (58)$$

$$b_2^2 = \frac{\alpha^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2 - 1} \left(\frac{q^2}{\alpha^2 - 1} - 1 \right) \quad (59)$$

Thus, the light beam in this case reproduces an ellipse (56), in one of the focuses of which the sun is located. Now it is clear that the replacement of (32) by (34) leads to the appearance of the product xy , which means the rotation of the main axis of the ellipse by some small angle $(-\Delta\varphi)$ relative to the coordinate axis OX .

Let us take the angle $\Delta\varphi$ so that

$$\mu_0 = \left(\frac{1}{b_2^2} - \frac{1}{a_2^2} \right) \times (-\Delta\varphi) \quad (60)$$

Whence, taking into account

$$\mu = \frac{b_2^2}{a_2^2} \epsilon^2 \Delta\varphi, \quad (61)$$

Where ϵ is the eccentricity of the ellipse.

$$\epsilon = \sqrt{1 - a_2^2/b_2^2} \quad (62)$$

Thus, the constant μ differs only by a constant factor from the rotation angle of the ellipse $\Delta\varphi$.

Substituting (60) into (57), we give the ellipse equation the form

$$\frac{x^2}{a_2^2} + 2 \left(\frac{1}{b_2^2} - \frac{1}{a_2^2} \right) \Delta\varphi \times xy + \frac{y^2}{b_2^2} = 1 \quad (63)$$

In turn, when passing from the Cartesian (x, y) to the polar coordinate system (ϱ, φ) , expression for (ϱ^2) , up to a value of the order of $(\Delta\varphi)^2$, takes the form

$$\varrho^2 = \frac{a_2^2}{1 - \epsilon^2 \sin^2(\varphi + \Delta\varphi)} \quad (64)$$

According to the optical-mechanical analogy, a material point will move along the same trajectory (64), which can be considered Mercury, comparing its sizes and the sun. If, in this case, the angle φ initially corresponded to the location of the ellipse, then after one revolution the description of the ellipse, as follows from (64), will be repeated not through 2π , but through $(2\pi - \Delta\varphi)$. In other words, the ellipse for the full period of revolution of the material point will undergo an angular displacement of $\Delta\varphi$.

Turning to the numerical estimate of the displacement (precession) of the perihelion of Mercury (identified with a material point in comparison with the sun), we first of all note that in

our model this displacement is affected only by the parameter μ . According to equality (104), the dimensions μ and $\Delta\varphi$ coincide, i.e., both parameters are expressed in angular units.

By varying the value of μ , we can, on the basis of (104), arrive at the observed value of $\Delta\varphi$. We have: semiaxis $b_2=0.387098$ astronomical units (a.u), semiaxis $a_2=0.378826$ a.u, eccentricity ϵ equal $\epsilon=0.205632$. The specified procedure leads to the value $\mu=0.00453''$. Then the angular displacement per one revolution of the planet will be $\Delta\varphi=0.1025''$. A tropical year is 365.2 days. Mercury's orbital period around the sun is 0.241 tropical years, or 88.01 Earth days. Therefore, Mercury makes 4.15 revolutions per year, and 415 revolutions per century. The perihelion shift over this period is $42.54''$. The resulting estimate is in agreement with the observed value of the perihelion shift (equal to $43.1'' \pm 0.5''$).

So, we see that the parameters included in the model under consideration lead (when they are varied) to complete coincidence with the quantities observed in astrophysics. Thus, the concept of using the entropic interaction and eikonal leads in the described phenomena to the same results as the General Theory of Relativity (and without resorting to models of gravity).

Mathematical abstractions are the space-time continuum in the theory of relativity, the use of Feynman diagrams [28] in quantum field theory, the standard model in the theory of elementary particles, multidimensional space in string theory, modeling of elementary particles using strings and identifying them with disturbances of scalar or other fields filling the World space.

On the other hand, the conservation laws we observe (energy, momentum, angular momentum, charge, and so on) are observable material entities, although they are described by mathematical abstractions, such as Noether's theorem, or gauge invariance in electrodynamics.

Returning to the mass defect, we note that with a decrease in the distance between bodies (and parts of the same body, i.e. with increasing density), their gravitational interaction increases, the binding energy increases, entropy decreases, the mass defect becomes larger, and we can imagine *the limiting case is when the mass defect is equal to the mass of the object*. I.e. bifurcation occurs, in which a material object is completely in a virtual state, its entropy increases abruptly and mass does not manifest itself in any way (i.e. is not observed).

An example is the mass defect of two *massive neutral vector bosons*, B^0 and W^0 , of which (according to the theory of electroweak interaction) photons, γ , consist of having zero rest mass [29]. The mass defect of these bosons completely cancels out their masses when they combine to form a photon, γ :

$$\gamma = B^0 \cos\theta_w + W^0 \sin\theta_w, \quad (65)$$

where θ_w electroweak angle (Weinberg angle), on which spontaneous breaking of electroweak symmetry rotates the initial plane of bosons W^0 and B^0 , creating as a result W^0 - boson and photon, γ .

In the case of a photon, not only the masses, but also the sizes of the bosons that make it up *do not appear*. Therefore, it is natural to assume that upon transition of material objects to the virtual state may *disappear* not only the observable their mass, but also their observable size. In other words, in a virtual state, material bodies can become point-like, invisible, and massless, not demonstrating any other observable properties.

Like virtual in *relation to each other* one should also consider objects that are so far apart from each other that any fundamental interaction between them can be neglected.

Objects rotating stationarily around their common center of mass can also be considered as *virtual relative to their center of mass*, meaning they lack observed gravitational attraction to this center of mass. In an expanding universe, such objects with mass, as a result of their entropic

interaction, should not only move away from each other, but also rotate around their common center of mass [30].

The mass defect can be explained by entropic interaction, which reduces the entropy of approaching material objects, and the associated increase in free energy.

Annihilation of particles and antiparticles can also be explained by their entropic interaction, i.e. the tendency to reduce free energy, which increases abruptly during a collision, since entropy decreases. A decrease in entropy leads to a mass defect equal to the total mass of annihilating particles, which pass into a virtual state, accompanied by a sharp increase in entropy and the simultaneous emission of gamma rays that conserve energy, momentum and their moments.

Similarly, the tendency to reduce free energy can explain the birth of new particles during collisions of elementary particles in accelerator experiments. Here the free energy decreases due to a sharp increase in entropy during the birth of new particles. (Before this, the total entropy of particles flying towards each other rapidly decreased, and their free energy increased.) At the same time, the rhythm of time for these particles sharply increases [18]. Therefore, in a reference frame at rest relative to them (in which we are, observing the birth of these particles), their lifetime is very short and the shorter, the greater the mass of the particles.

IX. Creation and evolution of the universe.

As mentioned above, the World space before the “Big Bang” should not be imagined as empty, but filled with a variety of non-visual (point-like) virtual objects. The space was infinite, homogeneous, isotropic (i.e. *unstructured*), had energy and the maximum possible entropy, and the masses, sizes and any other characteristics of the virtual objects contained in it did not manifest themselves in any way, because the resultant of all forces associated with their interaction was equal to zero. Despite the absence of real objects, *fullness of space by virtual objects* allows us to talk about the *physical vacuum having* energy of this space, consisting of structureless (“chaotic”) matter, sited in a virtual state, consisting of structureless (“chaotic”) matter. The random nature of the emission of energy quanta by these objects and their resulting chaotic movement led to fluctuations in their density. Besides these unimportant *reversible fluctuations in the density of virtual objects* and corresponding entropy fluctuations (required, in particular, by quantum mechanics) *in this vacuum no processes changing its state occurred. And the absence of such processes means the absence of time counting* [18]. But sometimes a single fluctuation or combination of fluctuations could become so strong that the previously existing organization no longer withstood and was collapsing. At this turning point, called special *bifurcation point* [31], it is fundamentally impossible to predict in which direction further development will occur: whether the state of the system will remain chaotic or whether it will move to a certain level of order. In other words, as a result of some *local* quantum fluctuations in vacuum density, the value of entropy and free energy in various *small areas of space* could change abruptly above a certain critical value. There could be any number of such areas and bifurcations. These bifurcations took place in a *random way* and were not coordinated with each other. After *reversible fluctuations in the density of virtual objects* the world space became *heterogeneous*. There was a certain structure (areas with increased or decreased density of virtual matter). Accordingly, the entropy of space decreased abruptly and its free energy increased. Bifurcation, naturally, occurred locally, but in accordance with Mach’s principle [32] (stating that local physical laws are determined by the large-scale structure of the universe and vice versa) it was reflected in the state of the entire world space. The state of space became unstable (due to an increase in its free energy) and the process of its evolution began. How did this happen?

As a result, “*structuring*”space (the appearance of areas with different densities of virtual objects in it), its entropy decreased (both locally and throughout space), and the resultant of the forces caused by the interaction of some of these objects ceased to be equal to zero. The mass of

these objects and their other characteristics (size, electrical charges, etc.) began to “*manifest*”, i.e. these objects began to move from virtual states to real ones. Selected directions appeared in space, along which forces began to act and under their influence the movement of objects arose. The entropy of space has decreased and the free energy has increased, making its state unstable, tending to decrease its free energy, increasing its entropy and simultaneously decreasing its internal energy. To implement this trend, objects, moving from a virtual state to a real one, continued to intensively emit “energy quanta,” which led to the appearance of temperature. As we have seen, having become real, these moving objects, initially concentrated in a *small area space, must run away*”, thereby realizing its entropy interaction (as if experiencing “*entropic repulsion*”, which Alan Guth called *negative gravity* [33]).

The Big Bang was the beginning of the countdown of a time in our universe. As a definition of time, it seems preferable to use its definition given by the famous physicist and philosopher Ernst Mach: “*Time is an abstraction that we come to by observing the change in objects of nature.*” This short and extremely capacious definition of time contains a deep meaning. First, it is argued that time is an abstract concept and does not represent some real entity. Secondly, it characterizes only a *change in the state of objects of nature* and is a parameter, with an increase in which this change occurs.

It is important to note that extrapolating the expanding universe to the initial period of its appearance associated with the Big Bang in *singularity point space* is not logically correct. The bifurcation that led to the Big Bang could not have happened at *the point space*. Quantum fluctuation of the density of virtual objects, by definition, occurs in some local *area having certain dimensions*. The singularity theorem [34], proved by Hawking, *only models characteristic features of the Big Bang process and is an abstract reality, not an objective (material) one*.

The bifurcation that led to the Big Bang and the birth of our universe sharply reduced the entropy of space, and the evolutionary process of expansion of the universe began to increase its entropy, which is still happening today. After a sufficiently long time, entropy will reach a certain maximum value, the interaction of all material objects will become negligible due to the excessively large distance between them, and they will find themselves in a virtual state *in relation to each other*. However, simultaneously with the expansion, the universe cools and as it approaches absolute zero, according to Nernst’s theorem, entropy stops changing and all processes stop. It can be expected that these two opposing effects will one day cause the expansion of the universe to cease. As a result, our universe will again find itself in a state equivalent to the state of world space that preceded the bifurcation that led to the Big Bang. One of the next bifurcations may initiate the birth of another universe. The process of its evolution will begin and all this will be repeated sporadically and indefinitely. This idea echoes Penrose’s approach to cyclicity in the behavior of the universe [35,36].

X. The concept of time. Relationship between the rhythm of time and changes in entropy.

It should be noted once again that, in accordance with existing today’s cosmological approaches [37,38], the initial (inflationary) stage of the evolution of the universe occurred very quickly (within small fractions of nanoseconds). However, taking into account the abrupt change in entropy as a result of bifurcation (first a sharp decrease in its value, and then an increase), which led to the Big Bang, it is necessary to take into account the accompanying sharp jump in the rhythm of time. Those from the position of the reference system located in the local region of the Big Bang (i.e. from the position of our distance of *the past*), the speeds of the processes that occurred there were not too high, as they look to us now (simply, at this stage of the development of the universe, the rhythm of time was many times faster than now).

Based on a simple assumption about the proportionality of the change in the probability of the state of an isolated non equilibrium system with constant internal energy and the time interval

during which this change occurs, in our article [18] was obtained consistency between the change in the entropy of the system and the course of time in that was repeat here.

Let some processes take place in a given isolated non-equilibrium thermodynamic system. By the time t_1 the state of this system is characterized by a certain set of physical characteristics. And let the probability of this state be W_1 . As a result of the processes occurring in the system, its state changes. Let us assume that the probability of this change ΔW on a small time interval Δt is proportional to the probability value of the given state W_1 and time Δt . It means

$$\Delta W = -\xi W_1 \Delta t$$

The minus sign means that after time Δt the probability of the system being in the initial state (i.e., with the same characteristics) will decrease. This equation can be rewritten as follows

$$\Delta W/W_1 = -\xi \Delta t, \quad (66)$$

or in the differential form

$$dW/W_1 = -\xi dt, \quad (67)$$

which should be solved under the following initial condition

$$W(t_1) = W_1 \quad (68)$$

Denoting the probability W_2 of the state formed by the end time t_2 ,

$$W(t_2) = W_2, \quad (69)$$

as a result, we get

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} dW/W = -\xi \int_{t_1}^{t_2} dt \quad (70)$$

and after integration we have

$$\ln W_1 - \ln W_2 = \xi(t_2 - t_1), \quad (71)$$

where ξ is the coefficient of proportionality with the dimension reciprocal of time. Since, for an isolated system, the logarithm of the probability of its state, taken with the opposite sign, ($-\ln W$), is (according to Boltzmann's H -theorem) up to a factor of $1/k$ is the entropy of the system s , we can rewrite this equation in the form

$$s_2 - s_1 = \Delta s_{2,1} = k\xi(t_2 - t_1) = k\xi\Delta t, \quad (72)$$

or

$$\Delta t = (1/k\xi)\Delta s_{2,1}, \quad (73)$$

where k is a proportionality factor equal to the Boltzmann constant k

($k=1.380\,649 \cdot 10^{-23} \text{ J K}^{-1}$). Thus, we come to the following conclusion:

Any process occurring in an isolated thermodynamic system with constant internal energy over time Δt , changes the entropy of the system by the value $\Delta s_{2,1}$ proportional to the time interval Δt . Thus, changes in entropy and time are interconnected and proportional to each other. Moreover, the change in entropy is positive, since the value $\Delta t = t_2 - t_1$ is always positive.

"That is, the entropy of an isolated nonequilibrium thermodynamic system with constant internal energy must increase with time and its change is proportional to the rhythm of time. The converse is also true: a change in the rhythm of entropy increasing leads to a corresponding change in the rhythm of time".

The passage of time is an abstract entity and is associated with the presence in the system of any processes that change its entropy and state. The absence of such processes and changes associated with them means the absence of the flow of time, its stopping. This is exactly how time was interpreted by Aristotle, who said: "*Time is unthinkable without change*". And in the middle of the last century, Schrödinger seemed to continue this idea, writing: "*An accelerated rate of entropy growth leads to a more intense life process*" [39], which increases the rhythm of time.

Universe, *generally*, and any set of its objects must move in space with some acceleration (because of "entropic repulsion"). In this case, the galaxies will move away from each other, thereby increasing the size of the universe and emitting the previously mentioned energy quanta non-uniformly. At the initial stage, associated with this observable, the mutual gravitational attraction of galaxies slows down this expansion, and when they move away, it becomes insignificant and "entropic repulsion" makes the expansion of the universe accelerated. Over time, the temperature of the universe decreases, the speed of movement increases, relativistic effects begin to affect, the state of the universe changes more slowly and it practically returns to the state that preceded the Big Bang, i.e. becomes equilibrium, homogeneous and isotropic, and then one of the possible bifurcations can lead it to the next Big Bang.

The value of entropy in different parts of a nonequilibrium thermodynamic system and, therefore, in an expanding universe is not the same and is of relative essence [18]. Accordingly, the rhythm of time in them should also be different. The farther these areas are from the observer, the greater their entropy and the faster time flows there. Therefore, the velocities of objects in these areas, measured in a reference frame at rest relative to them, will be overestimated. This may cast doubt on the significant excess discovered by astronomers in the orbital speed of rotation of stars and gas in galaxies from the distance to their center, which is now explained by the existence of dark matter, the absence of which in the formalism of the General Theory of Relativity (GTR) is considered by many to be a drawback of the theory. As a drawback of General Relativity, the absence in it of the concept of dark energy, which is used in current cosmology to explain the expansion of the universe, is also considered. *However, there are alternative theories (which include the approach outlined in this article, which explains the expansion of the universe by the random emission of energy quanta by all material objects).*

XI. Corpuscular-field formalism, its criticism and interaction of material objects.

It should be noted that since the introduction into physics of the concept of the electromagnetic field by Faraday and Maxwell, and then by Einstein of the gravitational field, everything is believed to be electrical, magnetic, "gravitational," or otherwise "*charged*" objects interact through their fields, each of which represents some continuous medium that transmits "from point to point" the force action of the corresponding charges on each other. The advent of quantum mechanics, and then nuclear physics and quantum field theory, made a significant addition to the field concept. It turned out that all physical fields consist of *quanta* (photons, mesons, not yet discovered gravitons, gluons and other elementary particles) that transfer field energy between interacting objects (moreover, it is these carriers of interaction that are considered virtual particles). Thus "*corpuscular-field dualism*", according to which every "*charge*" creates a force field, which is a continuous medium, but at the same time, this medium consists of discrete energy quanta. That is, the field is considered as a macroscopic object, "*confused*" with its energy quanta and described by a general wave function that obeys the Schrödinger equation. *Corpuscular-field dualism*, unlike the well-known *wave-particle duality*, is practically not discussed in the scientific literature, although it is present in it in the most direct way.

Considering "*corpuscular-field dualism*", let's try to find out how a real material object

that has some *energy charge*, acts on another object having a corresponding charge and how their (relatively speaking) force fields interact (electric, magnetic, gravitational, “nuclear - strong and weak” or any others). *Modern theoretical approaches do not yet have an acceptable answer to this question.*, although it is believed that the forces transferred from the field act on the object by virtual elementary particles and obeying Coulomb's law, or the law of universal gravitation, or nuclear interaction (strong or weak).

Which one really is, may be the nature of these forces? Consider, for example, how could there be a tendency of the disturbed (as a result of bifurcation) world space (with a sharply decreased entropy) to move into a more probable state.

It can be assumed that to implement this trend, all objects in space (virtual and real) emit energy quanta (photons, mesons, gravitons, etc.) in randomly selected directions and (after some time t_p , necessary for the propagation of these quanta) receive pulses from absorbed quanta emitted by neighboring objects. Before bifurcation, this radiation is random and isotropic in nature, due to the homogeneity and isotropy of space. After bifurcation, when the homogeneity and isotropy of space are violated, this random character is also violated.

Let us have two *real* objects *A* and *B* and each of them has some energy charge, which includes gravitational charge (mass), electric charge, “nuclear” and some others. These charges emit corresponding *energy quanta*. In other words, *all interactions between natural objects are realized by means of using the same quantized mechanism*. In the absence of any interaction, the radiation of the energy quanta is stochastic, i.e. all its directions are equally probable (as if there was only one object in space). With the emission of each quantum, objects receive reactive impulses (recoil impulses) in the direction opposite to the radiation (a type of Mössbauer effect). Due to the random nature of the radiation, recoil impulses received by objects, adding up vectorially, give a total impulse equal to zero. However, after the bifurcation leading to irreversible some indignation of the local *area of space*, *violating the uniform distribution of the density of point virtual objects located in it*, the vector sum of recoil impulse ceases *to be equal to zero*. In addition, after a certain time, quanta emitted by object *A* reach object *B*, and quanta from object *B* reach object *A*. The resonant part of these quanta (determined by the factor $\alpha < 1$) is absorbed and transfers its impulses to these objects, $P_{A \rightarrow B}$ and $P_{B \rightarrow A}$. At the initial moment after bifurcation, under the influence of all these impulses, objects scatter in different directions, *as if pushing away* from each other, realizing their entropic interaction, tending to increase their total entropy.

In *Inflationary theory* this is interpreted as a manifestation (at the initial time interval of the universe) *negative gravity*. In the language of geometry used in the theory of relativity, this means that space for some time (say t_p) was “convex” and then “turned on” “standard” gravitational interaction and space began to “bend” in the opposite direction, tending to become “flat”. The initial period of time is called inflationary. It is believed that during the “Big Bang” occurred, the universe appeared and began to expand exponentially. Using the quantum tunneling effect, *false* a vacuum began to penetrate into the universe, the density of which did not change during expansion, but the symmetry of space was broken and, as a consequence of this, elementary particles were born, which then united into atoms, molecules and macroscopic objects, including planets, stars and galaxies.

Using the assumption that was made above *about the emission of energy quanta* by all material objects, we can give a different explanation for the emerging interaction of objects and its random nature. In the absence of interactions between objects **A** and **B** their radiation is isotropic. Entropy of the space with these objects has a maximum value. The number of quanta emitted per unit time by each of the objects into the region surrounding them and outside it is the same and in a hypothetical one-dimensional case is equal $N_A/2$ and $N_B/2$, where N_A and N_B the

total number of quanta emitted by objects per unit time. When objects interact, their radiation becomes anisotropic and entropy decreases. This does not happen instantly, but after some time. During this short period, some of the quanta emitted by neighboring objects manage to reach the interacting object and transfer to it their impulses directed in the direction opposite to these objects. *The tendency initiated by entropic interaction* between objects to have the same concentration of energy quanta on both sides of each object reduces their radiation into the region between objects and, accordingly, increases radiation into the external region by the same amount (remember again the phenomena of diffusion and osmosis, leading to an increase in entropy and, accordingly, to a more equilibrium state). Therefore the number of quanta $N_{A \rightarrow B}$ emitted by object **A** depends on the number of quanta emitted by the object **B**, which in turn depends on $N_{A \rightarrow B}$. At the same time, the number of quanta $N_{A \rightarrow B}$ reaching the object **B**, is also proportional to the “charge” q_A object **A** and inversely proportional to the square of the distance r^2 between objects (due to the scattering of these quanta over the surface of a sphere of radius r). Probability of this event $W_{A \rightarrow B}$ proportional to the number $N_{A \rightarrow B}$. However, the object **B** absorbs not all quanta that reach it, but only those $\alpha N_{A \rightarrow B}$, $\alpha < 1$ who have *resonant energy*. The number of absorbed quanta, as well as the probability w_b this absorption must be proportional to the “charge” q_B object **B**. Probabilities $W_{A \rightarrow B}$ and w_B do not depend on each other. Hence, probability W_A radiation from an object **A** towards the object **B** quantum numbers $N_{A \rightarrow B}$ and absorption of part of these $\alpha N_{A \rightarrow B}$ quanta object **B** equal to the product of probabilities $W_{A \rightarrow B}$ and w_B :

$$W_A = W_{A \rightarrow B} w_B \sim \alpha q_a q_b / r^2 = \alpha m_a m_b / r^2 \quad (74)$$

According to *H*-theorem, $S = -k \ln W$. Consequently, if the masses of objects act as “charges”, we have from (74):

$$S = -k \ln W_A \sim -k \ln \alpha m_a m_b / r^2 = -k \ln \alpha m_a m_b + 2k \ln r, \quad (75)$$

So, when the $2k \ln r > k \ln \alpha m_a m_b$, their entropy S will grow and these masses will predominantly repel each other. When $2k \ln r < k \ln \alpha m_a m_b$, their entropy will decrease and these masses will predominantly attract each other.

Similar reasoning leads to the probability W_B radiation from an object **B** numbers $N_{B \rightarrow A}$ quanta in the direction of the object **A** with recoil impulse $P_{B \rightarrow A}$ and quantum numbers $N_{B \rightarrow out}$ in the opposite direction with recoil impulse $P_{B \rightarrow out}$. That is, $W_B = W_{B \rightarrow A} + W_{B \rightarrow out}$

Thus, the number of quanta emitted by an object **B** in the opposite direction to the object **A** with impulses $P_{B \rightarrow out}$ equals $N_B/2 + N_{A \rightarrow B}$, and towards the object **A** is emitted $N_B/2 - N_{A \rightarrow B}$ quanta with impulses $P_{B \rightarrow A}$. The difference in the number of quanta between these radiations is equal to $2N_{A \rightarrow B}$. Accordingly, for the object **B** difference $\Delta P_{B \rightarrow A}$ in recoil impulses from each emitted quantum is equal to

$$\Delta P_{B \rightarrow A} = P_{B \rightarrow out} - P_{B \rightarrow A} (1 + \alpha) > 0, \quad (76)$$

and directed towards the object **A**. Magnitude of the resulting force F , acting on the object **B**, is proportional to the total impulse received by it. Thus, the description given in the case of gravitational interaction of objects **A** and **B** leads them to mutual attraction (attraction in

accordance with Newton's law of universal gravitation (if the masses of objects act as "charges")):

$$F \sim m_a m_b / r^2. \quad (77)$$

The acceleration of objects will be slowed down.

As the temperature of material objects changes, the distribution (transmission) of energy quanta by them also changes.

For example, for objects of classical physics this happens (as mentioned earlier) incompatible with the Stefan-Boltzmann and Fourier laws. This changes the concentrations of these quanta on both sides of the objects and the intensity of their mixing. For example, if the temperature of the object A increased, it emits a greater number of quanta per unit time. Accordingly, the object B will emit a smaller number of quanta towards the object A and its recoil impulse to the side A will become larger, which will lead to an increase in its "attraction" to the object A .

The energy of gravitational interaction is considered "negative", because in order to "move" objects with masses in different directions, it is necessary to do some work, i.e. expend "positive" energy to overcome their gravitational attraction. As the distance between objects increases, their gravitational attraction decreases due to the redistribution of energy quanta radiation. This radiation increases towards the inside of the region surrounding the objects and decreases towards its outer part.

Reasoning similar to the above leads to the Coulomb attraction of objects with opposite electric charges. In this case, photons and radiation act as energy quanta, not *isotropic* (inside the area between objects it is less intense). For example, for objects of classical physics this happens (as mentioned earlier) in accordance with Fourier's law and it must be assumed that photons emitted by objects with negative charges are not absorbed by objects with positive charges and do not transfer their impulses to them. Likewise, negatively charged objects do not absorb photons emitted by positive charges.

In the case of charges of the same sign, to obtain the Coulomb interaction, the emission of photons by objects A and B , as we have already seen, leads to the repulsion of objects and increases their entropy.

Local areas where "Big Bangs" took place may also act as some objects, possible implementation of entropic interactions of which we have considered. The resulting universes must entropically interacting *run away*, i.e. (we speak conditionally) *entropically repel*, thus increasing the entropy of the world space, which has become structured. This "scattering" of universes excludes their "meeting" and interpenetration.

Applying the implementation of the entropic interaction described here to the Sun-Mercury system, one can obtain the observed shift of the perihelion of Mercury (which we realized in paragraph VIII using the eikonal), and applying it to double stars (pulsars), the shift of their periastron.

This is a possible addition to the generally accepted understanding of the origin of our universe and its subsequent evolution. The concept is not used fields, as a fundamental material entity and does not postulate the probabilistic nature of natural phenomena, but explained the use of the random nature of the emission of energy quanta by material objects, entropic interaction and the tendency of material objects to achieve an equilibrium state if they are not in it.

Same time, the opportunity to use the discrete emission of the energy quanta by all material objects can be considered as a possible quantization of gravity and three other fundamental interactions.

XII. Quasi-classical quantization of the gravitational field

1. System of interconnected equations of Schrödinger and Newton

Recall the main ideas of quasi-classical quantization of the gravitational field.

Newton's law of gravitation relatively to the spatially distributed gravitational potential is described by the Poisson equation:

$$\nabla^2 \varphi = 4\pi\gamma\varrho, \quad (78)$$

where γ is the gravitational constant, and ϱ – density of the medium.

In quantum mechanics a state of the system is determined by the probability $W(r,t)$ which is given by the square of the modulus $|\psi(r,t)|^2$ of the wave function $\psi(r,t)$:

$$W(r,t) = |\psi(r,t)|^2 \quad (79)$$

Function $\psi(r,t)$ satisfies non-stationary Schrödinger equation, which in the presence of gravitational field has the following form

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi(r,t)}{\partial t} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi(r,t) + U(r,t)\psi(r,t) \quad (80)$$

Function $\psi(r)$ satisfies stationary Schrödinger equation

$$\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi(r) + [E - U(r)]\psi(r) = 0 \quad (81)$$

The potentials $U(r,t)$ and $U(r)$ look like

$$U(r,t) = V(r,t) + m\varphi(r,t) \quad (82)$$

$$U(r) = V(r) + m\varphi(r) \quad (83)$$

where $V(r,t)$ and $V(r)$ - ordinary potentials, which represent the environment surrounding the particle, $\varphi(r,t)$ and $\varphi(r)$ - gravitational potentials, r is a vector that is a function of spatial coordinates $r=r(x,y,z)$, m is the mass of a point particle.

Value of the density ϱ of the medium in the Equation (78) has a form

$$\varrho = m|\psi|^2 \quad (84)$$

and the Poisson equation (78) can be written as:

$$\nabla^2 \varphi = 4\pi\gamma m|\psi|^2. \quad (85)$$

Equations (80) and (85), considered together, form the so-called Schrödinger-Newton system of equations. This system describes interconnected and mutually influencing quantum mechanical and gravitational fields.

Based on (84), the solution to equation (85) for the entire space has the form:

$$\varphi(r,t) = -\gamma m \int \frac{|\psi(r',t)|^2}{|r-r'|} dr', \quad (86)$$

where $r = (x, y, z)$, $r' = (\xi, \eta, \varsigma)$.

Substituting (86) into (80), we obtain one nonlinear Schrödinger-Newton integro-differential equation:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi(r,t)}{\partial t} = \left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 + V(r) - \gamma m^2 \int \frac{|\psi(r',t)|^2}{|r-r'|} dr' \right] \psi(r,t) \quad (87)$$

Research of various phenomena, predicted Equations (80), (85) and (87) are the subject of an extensive bibliography.

In particular, the use of the system of equations (80), (85) or equation (87) is natural when analyzing the influence of quantum mechanical laws on various aspects of the behavior of the gravitational field.

Let us next turn to the simplest special case of equation (81) – the stationary one-dimensional Schrödinger equation for the motion of one particle under the influence of a stationary one-dimensional potential, i.e. – to the equation

$$\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2 \psi(x)}{dx^2} + [E - U(x)] \psi(x) = 0, \quad (88)$$

in which

$$U(x) = V(x) + m\varphi(x). \quad (89)$$

At the same time, the potential $V(x)$ let's take it so that the potential $U(x)$ satisfactorily approximated a certain potential well for any gravitational potential $\varphi(x)$, obeying in this approximation the corresponding special case (83):

$$q(x) = m\psi^2(x) \quad (90)$$

and, in the role of (85) – to his Newton equation:

$$\frac{d^2 \varphi(x)}{dx^2} = \gamma q(x) \Rightarrow \frac{d^2 \varphi(x)}{dx^2} = \gamma m \psi^2(x). \quad (91)$$

2. Semiclassical approximation. Bohr–Sommerfeld quantization

For simplicity, we will consider equations (88) and (91) on a finite interval $[0, l]$, counting for (88) points $x = 0$ and $x = l$, so-called “turning points”, and for (91) – by accepting homogeneous boundary conditions of the 1st kind on them:

$$\varphi(0) = 0, \quad \varphi(l) = 0. \quad (92)$$

Consider now a semiclassical approximation of Bohr–Sommerfeld quantization. Following [4], let us carry out a formal substitution into (88):

$$\psi(x) = e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \sigma(x)}. \quad (93)$$

Then (88) turns into the equation:

$$\frac{1}{2m} \left[\frac{d\sigma(x)}{dx} \right]^2 - \frac{i\hbar}{2m} \frac{d^2 \sigma(x)}{dx^2} = E - U(x). \quad (94)$$

Since the system is assumed to be almost classical, we will look for a solution to equation (94) in the form of a series [41]:

$$\sigma(x) = \sigma_0(x) + \frac{\hbar}{i}\sigma_1(x) + \left(\frac{\hbar}{i}\right)^2\sigma_2(x) + \dots \quad (95)$$

As a first approximation, we neglect in (94), (95) the terms containing \hbar .

Then

$$\sigma(x) = \sigma_0(x), \quad (96)$$

$$\frac{1}{2m} \left[\frac{d\sigma_0(x)}{dx} \right]^2 = E - U(x), \quad (97)$$

and from (97) we deduce:

$$\sigma_0(x) = \pm \int \sqrt{2m[E - U(x)]} dx. \quad (98)$$

But the classic energies: complete energy E , potential energy $U(x)$ and kinetic energy $W = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$ of a particle moving at speed v , are related by the relation

$$E = W + U, \quad (99)$$

where

$$\sqrt{2m[E - U(x)]} = mv, \quad (100)$$

that is, the integrand in (98) is nothing more than a classical impulse $p = p(x)$ of particle in (88).

Hence,

$$\sigma_0 = \int p dx, \quad (101)$$

where

$$p = \sqrt{2m[E - U(x)]}, \quad (102)$$

and the momentum is defined here with a plus sign in front of the root.

In [41], the mathematical conditions and the corresponding physical meanings of the given approximation were analyzed in detail, and we will not repeat them here.

Accounting in (94) and (95) of the first order according to \hbar leads, using (16), to the equation

$$\sigma_0'(x)\sigma_1'(x) + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_0''(x) = 0 \quad (103)$$

or, taking into account (101) and (98), it leads to

$$\sigma_1'(x) = -\frac{\sigma_0''(x)}{2\sigma_0'(x)} = -\frac{p'(x)}{2p(x)}. \quad (104)$$

Integrating, we find:

$$\sigma_1(x) = -\frac{1}{2} \ln p(x) \quad (105)$$

(we omit an arbitrary constant).

Now substituting (101) and (105) into (93) and taking into account the signs in (98), we obtain after transformations a solution the wave function of the new approximation in the form [41]:

$$\Psi(x) = \frac{C_1}{\sqrt{p}} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \int p(x) dx} + \frac{C_2}{\sqrt{p}} e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} \int p(x) dx}. \quad (106)$$

In [41], further, it is shown that the found semiclassical expression of the wave function is advisable to consider it only in regions to the right of the turning point $x = 0$ and to the left of the turning point $x = l$, i.e. to have a deal based on (106) and be on real type of the function $\Psi(x)$:

$$\Psi(x) = \frac{C}{\sqrt{p}} \sin\left(\frac{1}{\hbar} \int_0^x p(\xi) d\xi + \frac{\pi}{4}\right) \quad \text{at } x > 0 \quad (107)$$

and

$$\Psi(x) = \frac{C}{\sqrt{p}} \sin\left(\frac{1}{\hbar} \int_x^l p(\xi) d\xi + \frac{\pi}{4}\right) \quad \text{at } x < l. \quad (108)$$

It is natural to require that (107) and (108) represent a unified description of the solution in the entire domain $[0, l]$. This is possible only if the following equations are satisfied:

$$\frac{1}{\hbar} \int_0^x p(\xi) d\xi + \frac{\pi}{4} = -\frac{1}{\hbar} \int_x^l p(\xi) d\xi - \frac{\pi}{4} + \pi(n + 1) \quad (109)$$

and $C = C'$, if the value n is even, and

$$\frac{1}{\hbar} \int_0^x p(\xi) d\xi + \frac{\pi}{4} = -\frac{1}{\hbar} \int_x^l p(\xi) d\xi - \frac{\pi}{4} - \pi(n + 1) \quad (110)$$

and $C = -C'$, if the value n is odd.

Relations (109) and (110), obviously, are combined into one:

$$= \frac{1}{\hbar} \int_0^l p(\xi) d\xi + \frac{\pi}{2} = \pi(n + 1) \quad (111)$$

(and $C = (-1)^n C'$).

Equality (111) represents the condition that determines the stationary states of a particle in the semiclassical approximation. This equality expresses the Bohr–Sommerfeld quantization rule (in the old quantum theory [40]).

As shown in [41], the corresponding normalized semiclassical wave function in the entire region $[0, l]$ appears in the form

$$\psi(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2\omega}{\pi v}} \sin\left(\frac{1}{\hbar} \int_0^x p(\xi) d\xi + \frac{\pi}{4}\right), \quad (112)$$

where $\omega = \frac{2\pi}{T}$ and T – frequency and period of classical periodic motion, and v is the corresponding particle velocity.

Considering (111) and (112) together, we see that the phase of the wave function (112) increases from $\frac{1}{4}\pi$ at the point $x = 0$ to $(n + \frac{3}{4})\pi$ at the point $x = l$, so the sine cancels in the interval $[0, l]$ smooth n times, or otherwise – an integer n is the number of zeros of the wave function (112), and therefore is the ordinal number of the stationary state.

It is obvious in this regard that the considered semiclassical approximation makes sense (applicable) only for large values n [41].

Thus, (112) is an expression of the quantized wave function, valid under all the assumptions made here.

3. Toward the quantization of the gravitational field

Turning now to the boundary value problem (91), (92), we note that the probability density following from the solution (112), i.e.

$$\psi^2(x) = \frac{2\omega}{\pi v} \sin^2\left(\frac{1}{\hbar} \int_0^x p(\xi) d\xi + \frac{\pi}{4}\right) \quad (113)$$

has zeros exactly matching the zeros of (112).

Consequently, the wave function (112) and the probability density (32) have the same quantization pattern. But then it immediately follows from (91) that exactly the same nature of quantization manifests itself in the quantity

$$\frac{d^2\varphi(x)}{dx^2}. \quad (114)$$

What follows then regarding the gravitational potential $\varphi(x)$ itself?

To answer this question, it is necessary to have a solution to problem (91), (92).

By using direct finite integral transformation [42, 43]

$$\overline{\varphi}(\lambda_k) = \int_0^l \varphi(\xi) \sin \lambda_k \xi d\xi, \quad \lambda_k = \frac{\pi k \xi}{l}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots \quad (115)$$

and reverse transformation

$$\varphi(x) = \frac{2}{l} \sum_{\lambda_k} \sin \lambda_k x \overline{\varphi}(\lambda_k) \quad (116)$$

(taking here for simplicity $l = 1$) we come to the following solution:

$$\varphi(x) = \gamma m \int_0^1 \psi^2(\xi) G(x, \xi) d\xi \quad (117)$$

where Green's function $G(x, \xi)$ is the following [43]

$$G(x, \xi) = -\frac{2}{\pi^2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin \pi k x \sin \pi k \xi}{k^2} = -(1-x)\xi, \quad \text{if } x \geq \xi \quad (118)$$

and

$$G(x, \xi) = -\frac{2}{\pi^2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin \pi k x \sin \pi k \xi}{k^2} = -(1-\xi)x, \quad \text{if } x \leq \xi \quad (118a)$$

Substituting (113) into (117) taking into account the expressions in (118) and (118a), we finally obtain:

$$\varphi(x) = -\gamma m \frac{2\omega}{\pi v} \int_0^1 \sin^2 \left(\frac{1}{h} \int_0^{\xi} p(\eta) d\eta + \frac{\pi}{4} \right) \times (1-\xi)x d\xi, \quad \text{if } x \leq \xi \quad (119)$$

and

$$\varphi(x) = -\gamma m \frac{2\omega}{\pi v} \int_0^1 \sin^2 \left(\frac{1}{h} \int_0^{\xi} p(\eta) d\eta + \frac{\pi}{4} \right) \times (1-x)\xi d\xi, \quad \text{if } x \geq \xi \quad (119a)$$

When taking out the integral sign expressions containing x , we see that inside this integral there remain only expressions containing ξ . This means that the dependence of the gravitational potential $\varphi(x)$ itself from coordinate x is piecewise monotonic in nature, and, unlike (114), does not exhibit any quantization. This result was a consequence of our use of model (85), (91).

But the quadratic dependence $\frac{d^2\varphi(x)}{dx^2}$ from $\psi(x)$ adopted in (85) and, accordingly, in (91) is not the only possibility of constructing the approximation.

Thus, the Schrödinger equation (88) included in the model (considered from right to left) suggests that, as an alternative to (90), as a density $\varrho(x)$ it is advisable to study not only the linear relationship $\varrho(x)$ with probability density $\psi^2(x)$, but also a similar dependence $\varrho(x)$ from the wave function $\psi(x)$ itself, taking into account (100) that

$$\varrho(x) = \alpha m \frac{p^2}{h^2} \psi(x), \quad (120)$$

where α – proportionality coefficient. Then instead of (88) we will have:

$$\frac{d^2\varphi(x)}{dx^2} = \gamma \varrho(x) \Rightarrow \frac{d^2\varphi(x)}{dx^2} = \gamma \alpha m \frac{p^2}{h^2} \psi(x). \quad (121)$$

From the second equation (121) and equation (112) it follows that when $p > 0$ the value $\frac{d^2\varphi(x)}{dx^2}$ is still quantized in the same way as solution (112).

But from (88) and (100) it follows:

$$-\frac{p^2}{h^2} \psi(x) = \frac{d^2\psi(x)}{dx^2}. \quad (122)$$

Therefore, the second of the equations in (121) turns into the differential equation

$$\frac{d^2\varphi(x)}{dx^2} = -\gamma \propto m \frac{d^2\psi(x)}{dx^2}, \quad (123)$$

viewed in relation to $\varphi(x)$ all with the same boundary conditions (92).

Applying to (123) and (92) ($l = 1$) transformations (115), (116), we find that this time

$$\varphi(x) = -\gamma \propto m \int_0^1 \frac{d^2\psi(\xi)}{d\xi^2} G(x, \xi) d\xi, \quad (124)$$

but with the same Green's function (118). Taking advantage of $G(x, x)$ by the expression in (118), we have:

$$\varphi(x) = \gamma \propto m \int_0^1 \frac{d^2\psi(\xi)}{d\xi^2} \frac{2}{\pi} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin \pi k x \sin \pi k \xi}{k^2} d\xi. \quad (125)$$

Integration by parts twice transforms (125) into

$$\varphi(x) = -\gamma \propto m \int_0^1 \psi(\xi) \left\{ \frac{2}{\pi} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sin \pi k x \sin \pi k \xi \right\} d\xi. \quad (126)$$

But according to [43]:

$$\frac{2}{\pi} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sin \pi k x \sin \pi k \xi = \delta(\xi - x). \quad (127)$$

Then

$$\varphi(x) = -\gamma \propto m \int_0^1 \psi(\xi) \delta(\xi - x) d\xi = -\gamma \propto m \psi(x). \quad (128)$$

Finally, substituting (112) into (128), we establish:

$$\varphi(x) = -\gamma \propto m \sqrt{\frac{2\omega}{\pi v}} \sin \left(\frac{1}{\hbar} \int_0^x p(\xi) d\xi + \frac{\pi}{4} \right). \quad (129)$$

Thus, the gravitational potential $\varphi(x)$ acquires quantization, which differs only by a constant factor from the quantization (112) of the wave function.

In conclusion, we present additional information from [41]: “Based on the quantization rule (111), we can find out the general nature of the level distribution in the energy spectrum. Let ΔE is the distance between two adjacent levels, i.e. levels with quantum numbers n differing by the value one”. In [41] it is shown that in the accepted approximation we have

$$\Delta E = \hbar\omega. \quad (130)$$

And further: “For a number of neighboring levels (the difference in numbers n which is small compared to itself n) corresponding frequencies ω can be considered approximately the same. Therefore... in each small section of the quasi-classical part of the spectrum the levels are located equidistantly, at equal intervals $\hbar\omega$ ”.

But this conclusion is obviously also valid for the energy spectrum of the gravitational potential (129), which also has (due to the inclusion of (112)) the quantization rule (111).

XIII. Quantization of the gravitational field generated by entropic interaction

Considering the general picture of the Schrödinger-Newton equations, we see that in the role of density ρ , acting due to the Poisson equation (78) on the distribution of gravitational potential φ , acts (see (79)) as a quantity proportional to the probability density $|\psi|^2$. The latter, in turn, is generated by the Schrödinger equation (80). But in accordance with the Boltzmann H-theorem, the probability density $|\psi|^2$ is one-to-one related to the corresponding entropy S . Therefore, statements that the influence on gravity of density in the form (78), and the influence on it of the indicated entropy S , turn out to be equivalent in the general case described here.

In the light of what has been said, let us turn to a specific result: the quantization of the gravitational field. Thus, the first equation (121) means that impact of the type $\gamma \rho(x)$ is going to the structure responsible for the nature of the gravitational potential. The second, is that this effect is proportional to the wave function $\psi(x)$, created by the Schrödinger equation (written, for example, in the form (122)). But $\psi(x)$ is related to the Boltzmann entropy in the following way:

$$S(x) = -k \ln |\psi(x)|^2, \quad (131)$$

Therefore,

$$\psi(x) = \left[|\psi|^2(x) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} = \left[e^{-\frac{1}{k}S(x)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (132)$$

(here the fractional exponent is deliberately written above the square bracket in order to emphasize that, in accordance with (112), the value of the square root also takes on different signs for different x).

Thus, (131) is complemented by one more representation

$$\frac{d^2\varphi(x)}{dx^2} = \gamma \propto m \frac{p^2}{\hbar^2} \left[e^{-\frac{1}{k}S(x)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (133)$$

meaning that the structure located on the left side of the first formula (40) experiences entropic influence. In this case, the sequence of actions (40) – (48) due to equality (51) (read from right to left) is completely preserved. In other words, and in this qualitative construction, the statement that the quantization of the gravitational field is generated by the wave function of the Schrödinger equation, and the statement that exactly the same quantization is created by the entropic interaction, are also equivalent.

XIV. Combining the Schrödinger and Fokker-Planck equations into one entropy structure.

The Fokker-Planck equation describes the evolution in time of the probability density $w(r,t)$, and the Schrödinger equation describes the change in time and space of the pure state specified by the wave function $\psi(r,t)$. The above equations have some common features. Let us show the fundamental possibility of the existence of at least a subclass of these equations, combined in the entropy representation into a single structure, i.e. into one equation.

In the one-dimensional version, the solution to the Schrödinger equation for a free particle can be represented in the factorized form

$$\Psi(x, t) = \Psi(x) e^{-i \frac{Et}{\hbar}} \quad (134)$$

where E is the total energy of the particle, and $\Psi(x)$ satisfies the stationary Schrödinger equation

$$\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2 \Psi(x)}{dx^2} + E \Psi(x) = 0 \quad (135)$$

The expression (134) shows that the probability density of detecting a particle at point x is

$$|\Psi(x, t)|^2 = \Psi(x, t) \Psi(x, t)^* = \Psi^2(x) \quad (136)$$

One of the variants of the initial-boundary value problem for the simplest Fokker-Planck equation is written in the form

$$\frac{\partial Q(x, t)}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial^2 Q(x, t)}{\partial x^2} = 0 \quad (137)$$

$$Q(0, t) = 0, \quad Q(l, t) = 0 \quad (138)$$

$$Q(x, 0) = Q_0(x) \quad (139)$$

The Green's function of problem (137)-(139) looks like this:

$$G(x, \xi, t) = \frac{2}{l} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sin \lambda_n x \sin \lambda_n \xi e^{-\lambda_n^2 t}, \quad (140)$$

where $\lambda_n^2 = \frac{\pi^2 n^2}{l^2}$ - eigenvalues of the corresponding Sturm-Liouville problem. It is obvious that when $0 < l \ll 1$ and $t > 0$, it is permissible to save in the Equation (140), as a first approximation, only the first spatio-temporal mode. To describe the function $Q(x)$, we accept the following factorization:

$$Q(x, t) = Q(x) e^{-\lambda_1^2 t} \quad (141)$$

Substituting (141) into (137) shows that $Q(x)$ satisfies the following stationary equation

$$\frac{d^2 Q(x)}{dx^2} + \lambda_1^2 Q(x) = 0 \quad (142)$$

The solution to this equation subject to the normalization

$$\int_0^l Q(x) dx = 1 \quad (143)$$

looks like

$$Q(x) = \frac{\pi}{2l} \sin \frac{\pi}{l} x \quad (144)$$

Note that although equations (135) and (142) are mathematically identical, physically they are qualitatively different, as are the functions $\Psi(x)$ and $Q(x)$, for which these equations were obtained.

According to Boltzmann H-theorem entropy $S(x)$ is proportional to probability density $w(x)$:

$$S(x) = -k \ln Q(x) \quad (145)$$

and the following expression is true

$$Q(x) = |\psi(x)|^2 \quad (146)$$

In this case we have

$$\psi(x) = e^{-\frac{1}{2k}S(x)} \quad (147)$$

Substituting (147) into (135) we get the equation

$$\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} e^{-\frac{1}{2k}S(x)} + E e^{-\frac{1}{2k}S(x)} = 0 \quad , \quad (148)$$

which transfers to the following equation as a result of some transections

$$-\frac{d^2S(x)}{dx^2} + \frac{1}{2k} \left(\frac{dS(x)}{dx}\right)^2 + \frac{4mkE}{\hbar^2} = 0 \quad (149)$$

As a result, the Schrodinger equation (135) in terms of entropy (145) took the form (149).

Quality $W(x) = Q(x)$ corresponds to the Fokker-Planck equation (142). From (145) we find out

$$Q(x) = e^{-\frac{1}{k}S(x)} \quad (150)$$

Substituting (150) into (142), we obtain the equation

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} e^{-\frac{1}{k}S(x)} + \lambda_1^2 e^{-\frac{1}{k}S(x)} = 0 \quad (151)$$

which, as a result of transformations, turns into the equation

$$-\frac{d^2S(x)}{dx^2} + \frac{1}{k} \left(\frac{dS(x)}{dx}\right)^2 + k \lambda_1^2 = 0 \quad (152)$$

Thus, the Fokker-Planck equation (142) took the form (152) in terms of entropy (145). Comparing (149) and (152), we see that they differ only in the values of the constant coefficients. Using the same notation for these coefficients, we arrive at one equation:

$$-\frac{d^2S(x)}{dx^2} + a^2 \left(\frac{dS(x)}{dx}\right)^2 + b^2 = 0 \quad , \quad (153)$$

where a^2 and b^2 are constant coefficient for both equations (149) and (152).

Used without additional information, this equation does not make it possible to distinguish from which equation (142) or (145) it is derived. Thus, thanks to the transition to the entropy representation, two completely different physical laws, described by different equations, were

transformed into one equation (153) regarding entropy. By returning to the specific coefficients in (153) and the corresponding relations (14) and (150), either the Schrödinger equation or the Fokker-Planck equation is restored (in reverse) from equation (153).

Thus, using entropy interaction, it is possible to describe both quantum and relativistic mechanics within the framework of one approach proposed in this article, and this together with result of the previous paragraph and along with the discrete emission of gravitation quanta by all material objects should be considered as the quantization of gravitational interaction.

XV. Conclusion.

It is shown how the introduction of entropic interaction as a fifth fundamental interaction and the essence factor in natural processes explains and allows us to quantify observed phenomena, starting with the measurement process and continuing with relativistic and quantum effects, the origin of the universe, and the quantization of gravity together with other fundamental interactions. Another important conclusion following from equation (75): when $k \ln \alpha m_a m_b > 2k \ln r$ the mutual attraction of objects with mass contributes to the formation of chemical elements and macroscopic objects consisting of them, and the fulfillment of the inequality $k \ln \alpha m_a m_b < 2k \ln r$, determines the probability of their moving away from each other, which should be considered as the reason for the expansion of the universe. When objects move away from each other at a sufficiently large distance, entropy of the world space began to have a maximum value, emission of energy quanta by all material objects becomes almost identical in all directions (isotropic), i.e. it approaches the situation that preceded the Big Bang and world space can again be considered homogeneous and isotropic, until the next bifurcation will lead to a new Big Bang explosion.

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